

THE IMPORTANCE OF INTEGRATING LANGUAGE SKILLS IN THE PROCESS OF TEACHING ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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Abstract: This research paper studies the significance of integration of language skills into the teaching English language. Also, this article highlights integrating language skills focusing on the main four English skills - reading, writing, speaking and listening – with the help of the “Communicative Language Teaching” methodology. Integrating language skills is concerned with authentic communication, insolate language students' realistic language and difficulties for them to interact naturally in the language. This technique promotes teachers to develop learners' achievements in multiple skills at a similar time. The research of authentic content is motivated by integrating language skills not just the dissection of language forms.

Keywords: integrating language skills, integration, language, skills, methodology, communicative, methods, instruction, communication, educational material.

I. Introduction

Integrating language skills are the building steps and effective parts in the process of language achievement. In accordance with build the countywide and compound process of language study simple and productive, integration skills can be an integral section of instructing language. Integrating language skills promotes foreign language learners to improve their skills in applying two or more of the four skills (i.e. listening, speaking reading and writing) in contexts and real life situation. A high level of professional training is an urgent task of modern higher education. One of the aspects of this problem is the formation of the readiness of the future teacher to solve professional problems, which is a key component of professional problems. Generality of structure connections between the educational and professional activities of undergraduates contributes to the differentiation of these types of activities. The content of educational and professional activities is differ. A characteristic of professional activity is labor activity aimed at the production of spiritual or material values. Educational activity is aimed at the formation of cognitive qualities and motivation to receive information as a sign system.

For supporting much focused and important learning cases, during teaching and practicing the language, teachers must integrate the four language skills. English language is utilized as a applying language along with national or regional formal languages for communication and correlations in educational universities, institutions, other organizations such as banks, hospitals, industries, government and non-governmental organizations, unnecessary to note the comprehensive usage on the language to carry out trade between and among the diplomatic missions, international affairs and relations offices. It is demanded that students who graduating colleges and universities require to

own skills of the foreign language with sufficient theoretical and practicable awareness and much practices on integrating its four skills - writing, speaking, listening and reading [10;54]. This is as the perfect order they have on integrated skills could possess an important and lasting impact on increasing their academic achievements. As a consequence, the application of integrated skills in a student-centered and authentic fashion is significant as it allows students to improve their communicative skills. Scientists increased engagement in carrying out this research to identify the degree of attempts applied by foreign language teachers towards gaining the integrating language skills while teaching of English lessons. In this relationship, the subsequent causes can be referred [4;170]. The first, it is one of the important sphere that foreign language teachers usually face issues in reaching the language skills integrations. The second, there is not any room for a language teacher to cope with distinct language skills favoring one over the other. Moreover, many teachers think that students can take advantages more when they are interested in studying integrated language skills than segregated ones.

II. Literature review

It is evident that in the teaching and learning process all these language skills are beneficial and a complexion of the language skills has a plus impact on the learners' development (Selma and Selen, 2010) [3;370]. In classroom atmosphere, skills require to be integrated, applied and practiced. According to Hinkel (2006), communication will be meaningful if it happens in integrated language skills, not through an isolated one. That is, if language learners apply only one language skill at a time, communication among language learners does not run well. So, in the teaching language procedure and in real life situation language skills should also be integrated. Thence, for supporting much focused and important learning cases, during teaching and practicing the language, teachers must integrate the four language skills. Nunan (1989) emphasized the requiring for building definite relationship between instructions of classroom language and tasks of real world so as to increase language proficiency of students [2;6].

In the beginning of 20th century, language teaching specialists have employed a whole language approach, concentrates on teaching the four skills. This technique was designed in the 1980s and put into practice for language teaching in the 1990s and the 2000s, specifically by US educators (Hinkel, 2006; Selma and Selen, 2010). It is thought as an approach as it has main structures about language in general and teaching/learning language by integrated reading, writing, listening and speaking in particular. Richards and Rodgers (2001) considered, the whole language teaching approach was increased to assists teaching English as a second/ foreign language to young learners at primary, young learners at junior, secondary and tertiary levels of education [6;115]

Today, the integrating four language skills in the teaching-learning of English is applied widely in many countries of the world. This application is gradually exporting to cover other parts of the universe (Brown, 2001; David, 1994; Oxford, 2001). Currently, the education system often uses an integrated approach for teaching various subjects. E.Yu. Sukharevskaya defines integration as subordination to the single goal of educating

and teaching similar parts and elements of the content, methods and forms within the educational system at a certain level of education (preschool, primary, secondary, senior) [5;90]. A. A. Zagorodnova writes that integration in vocational training is the interpenetration and mutual enrichment of professional areas. She notes that integration is accompanied by the complexity and consistency of pedagogical phenomena and professions [2;8]. In 1983, the topic of integration in education is considered in the collection of scientific papers "Integrative Processes in Pedagogical Science and Practice of Communist Education and Education". According to the authors, the first attempt was made to reflect the essence of this process in pedagogical science. In modern education, an integrated approach continues to develop. We believe that the application of this approach is the most appropriate in the study of various subjects, especially foreign languages. V.A. Shershneva writes that the exercises are proposed in textbooks, they should have real practical value, which allows them to look informal and arouse interest among students using a computer to solve practical problems, perform lexical, phonetic exercises. Performing exercises using technical means enhances the practical orientation of both the subject of a foreign language and the subject of computer science. It should be noted that integrative approaches reflect modern research methods in these branches of scientific knowledge and contribute to the sustainable interest of students in the subjects studied [7;86].

III. Methods

For this investigation, research of the descriptive survey was designed with applying both qualitative and quantitative approaches. Primarily using study, quantitative data was identified, analyzed and made conclusions concerning the sample of implementing of integration language skills in the procedure of teaching and learning foreign language. On this purpose, information were carried out with utilizing structured and open-ended questionnaires, observations, semi-structured interviews and document/content analysis of the teaching material/module. Accordingly, the scientists prepared a checklists of classroom observation to possess firsthand data concerning the implementation of language skills integration, and to submit extra data and appropriate results owned through other instruments.

IV. Discussion

While conducting English lessons, EFL teachers were discovered not paying enough focus to practicing the implementing of integrated language skills due to the following reasons. Firstly, background knowledge or experience of the students' in owning language in a separate way in high schools did not encourage them to do so. Secondly, proficiency of learners' in utilizing the four language skills seemed to be uneven, which is crucial due to challenges observed in voicing their opinions in speech and writing. Thirdly, the scarcity and inadequacy of context of instructional teaching materials, specifically modules, negatively influenced on the implementation of integrated language skills. Some studies have been carry out in the sphere of listening, speaking,

reading and writing skills however without considering their interdependence during language teaching.

To this impact, the scientists formulated the subsequent investigation questions to be answered in the course of the study:

1. To what scope do teachers possess enough awareness on the theoretical orientations of language skills integration in the classroom?
2. How frequently is the integrating language skills' teaching practically applied in EFL classrooms?
3. What are the main causes blocking of the implementing of integrating language skills integrations in the classrooms?

When conducting integrated classes in English in the master's program, teacher can create a basis for the further formation of a lexical and grammatical base, pronunciation and intonation skills. Integrated English language courses form a communicative-cognitive motive that contributes to the formation of professional competence and successful professional activity. All its aspects are subject to communicative goals. The main goal is to teach a foreign language as a means of communication. Starting to develop various kinds integrated courses, it is necessary to have a clear idea of the structure of the proposed educational activities, educational trajectory; define a common system of interdisciplinary concepts, develop main stages of activity.

This process involves the construction of a holistic model and strategy of the educational process, as well as a systematic analysis of activities. Among the educational tasks, one should single out the selection of material, specific sections and topics, establishing interdisciplinary links, representing the possibility of implementing principles of integration in education. Integrated English course contributes to the acquisition of theoretical knowledge and their practical implementation in the process of professional activity of a master student. In integrated courses, English is a means of acquiring knowledge in other disciplines. The integration of education creates a unified system of knowledge, skills and abilities, which helps to form professional competence among undergraduates. Integrated lessons allow teaching undergraduates communicative functions within the framework of a speech act, without breaking away from reality, which allows using daily situations for expression or requesting various information. A feature of the foreign language component undergraduate training programs in the aspect integration into professional activity is the introduction of special vocabulary, consideration of the features of reading and writing scientific texts, solving educational problems, discussing professional issues tasks. Integrative learning takes place in the context of active professional communication on topics related to undergraduate research.

V.Results

This procedure necessitates the model's design and principle of the educational process, moreover a systematic analysis of activities. Several educational tasks. Teaching material's result depicts that many respondents want integrated language skills in teaching foreign language. It is shown in the Table 1.

Table 1

Content	Percentage	Category
Integrated language skills	88.99%	Compulsory
English vocabulary	78.99%	Compulsory
Written to spoken	78.15%	Compulsory
Reproduction reading into writing or speaking	64,20%	Compulsory
English grammar	63.87%	Compulsory

From the results of research in the Table 1, it is found that large number of respondents (88,99%) considered appropriate usage of integrated language skills in the teaching language leads to an excellent results. And also, many respondents (78,99%) wanted that the achievement of vocabulary building of English language due to the content of teaching materials. Written to spoken (78,15%) is more popular aspects in including material that teaching foreign language. Many respondents (64,20%) wanted reproduction reading into writing or speaking should be in the teaching material to be improved. 63.87% respondents gave the opinion about English grammar must be in the development teaching material.

VI. Conclusion

On basis of the basic findings of the research, the subsequent conclusions are drawn.

- The language teachers barely taught the four language skills to gain integration in speaking, writing listening and reading lessons. For this aim, it is obvious that teachers carrying out EFL classes were frequently using a lonely/separate language skills mode of instruction at the expenditure of integrated language skills. It is not enough of theoretical orientations and practical awareness on the establishment and distribution of EFL lessons which was solely responsible for difficulties encountered in the implementation and achievement of integration of language skills in the teaching of English as a Foreign Language.

- From the perspective of teaching and learning in integrated language skills lessons, communicative tasks - information gap, role play have important in that they assure learners practice integration of two or more language skills simultaneously and actively engage in the procedure of teaching-learning integrated language skills in classrooms and establish an authentic language atmosphere that encourage positive student-to- student and teacher-to-student interactions

- The sharing proper teaching material/module in encouraging the integration of language skills in language classrooms is quite definite. However, the current research depicted that the lack of such a tool that limited teachers' power in planning lesson and proper lesson implementation that would assure integrated language skills teaching become successful.

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